

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ISSUES OF LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: *This scientific article shows the similarities differences between the cases in English and Uzbek. Through this article, several problems related to grammar are proven to some extent. The article gives examples from Uzbek and English language. The aim is to compare the terminology and approaches used in each language.*

Keys words: *cases, nominativ, genitive, accusative, dative, locative, ablative cases.*

Grammar plays a crucial role in effective communication in the English language. Studying grammar not only enhances one's writing and speaking skills but also contributes to a deeper understanding of the language itself. But learners may have difficulties when they need to compare their native language with foreign one, in our case with the English. In this article we are going to compare some cases with negative connotation in English and Uzbek languages with grammatical point of view. The problem of the number of cases in English has given rise to different theories which were based on different ways of approaching the description of English grammatical structure. In theory, two cases include in English counted as: nominative, genitive cases. [3:20]. There are six cases in the Uzbek language, each of which has a name and a form: bosh kelishik (nominative case), qaratqich kelishik (genitive case), tushum kelishik (accusative case), jo'nalish kelishik (dative case), o'rin- kelishik (locative case), chiqish kelishik (ablative case). [2:237]

*Let alone a **cake**-but to ignore it completely... [4;5]*

*Bu orada kunlar isib, **bahor** kerib keldi. [1;405]*

As it is possible to from the example above in both English and Uzbek languages **cake** and **bahor** were used in nominative case (bosh kelishik) zero morphemes [3;21].

***Weagley's eyes**, that was very wrong... [4;82]*

*Oti Onabibi bo'la qolsin ...**Opamning oti**, - dedi. [1;65].*

Genitive (qaratqich kelishik) is formed in English with 's, this case denotes possession of a thing or person [3;21]. In Uzbek language, it is formed with the suffix **-ning** and it is an answer to one of the questions of **kimning?** (whose), **nimaning?**(what's), **qayerning?**(where are) and the word after it takes a possessive suffix Genitive case is used in marked and unmarked forms. [2;239].

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In addition there are four way of cases accusative (tushum kelishik), dative case (jo'nalish kelishik), locative case (o'rin-payt kelishik), ablative (chiqish kelishik) in Uzbek.

Give me my friends' latter. [4;14]

Chol belbog'ining qatidan xatni chiqardi. [1;99]

Accusative case (tushum kelishik) is made with the suffix **-ni**. Accusative case is used in marked and unmarked forms. The question forms are **kimni?**(whom) or **nimani?**(what) [2;243].

I daresay you'd rather go to school... [4;82]

Orif aka ertasiga maktabga bordi. [1;98]

In English are not have the suffix dative case (jo'nalish kelishik). In Uzbek, it is made with the suffix **-ga** or **qayerga?** (where to) answer the question. [2;244] It can be rendered in English also by means of prepositions **to, at, into,** etc.

You have been wondering whether I put you in the house. [4;134]

Uyda Sharofat xola kasal. [1;324]

Locative case (o'rin-payt kelishik) denotes the place of the thing or a person in the space and it can be rendered in English by means of preposition **at, in, an, by** etc. The locative case exists in Uzbek and it has one orthographic **-da** and two orthographic variants- **ta. Qayerda** (where) answer the question. [2;246]

Letters from school. [4;29]

Xorazmdan keldim. [1;205]

Ablative case (chiqish kelishik) this is case suffix **-dan** and **kimdan?** (from whom), **nimadan?** (from what,) **qayerdan?** (from where) will be an answer to one of the questions. [2;247] It can be rendered in English by means of preposition **from, out from, from under,** etc.

Conclusion: To sum up, comparison of any two languages which can be Uzbek and English has grabbed attention of many students. Cases are one the interesting as well as necessary theme for both Uzbek and English students. The reason of that a great number of other themes are correlated to this theme such as noun, pronoun, part of speech and so on. English and Uzbek languages is different because former belongs to analytical the other to synthetic type of languages.

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